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“WE ARE STEWARDS OF THIS LIFE’S ZEST”

As cliché as it sounds, “Health is Wealth” equates “Nurture Nature”. Everyone knows, nature’s ripple effect when it finally gets so used and abused. Through our care, we breathe positively yet survived constantly. But what we people know about nurture? Maybe, some are so into caring it, while others may take for granted its some aspects of it.

To start, to nurture nature emerges the benefit of unlocking the doors of traveling. In fact, traveling is nothing without the glimpse of nature surrounding and making it so therapeutic. Also, if not for this life’s zest, then we would not be alive and claiming life as it is. Thus, we have to nurture the nature we live in. The ecosystem where people gathered together in which the plants, consumers, and decomposers work together in their environment for survival should make every human being proactive and keen towards keeping it safe and free from harmful effects of pollution, the cons it brings during deforestation, and all others may it be in sea or in land. Undeniably, if we don’t be proactive stewards, it is so harder to ask much on nature. Nature provides us great therapy such as food, water, medicinal and herbal plants. Not to mention, the fabrics and tangible materials it gives us when we want to lie down, minimalist our house and home, providing spaces we dreamed to be own. Precisely, nature interacts us such a promising beauty of which our response must be of caring heaven-scantly. Let us always remember that the moment we hurt what we supposed to nurture, cannot be replenished in a shortest time possible. As humans we are, harder to forgive and so hard to forget, corresponds our Mother Nature, who gives us this “Life’s Zest” to firmly stand with our responsibility to help save the nature around us. To continue build sustainable society, in heart and in soul, put it in mind that the 3R’s will never go wrong, reduce, reuse, and recycle. Wake up, and continue nurturing despite of living this digital age, our beloved nature.

Nevertheless, as stewards of this life’s zest, we should take care of nature so that nature can continue to take care of us. As such, *nemo dat quod non habet*, we cannot give what we do not have and to ignite that, we should embrace simple living while going back to the basics of life’s adage.